

Stoichiometry and Stability of Ti (IV) Chelate of Bidentate Ligand, *p*-Dimethyl Amino Anil of 3-Phenanthryl Glyoxal

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The stoichiometry of Ti (IV) chelate of *p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal has been determined spectrophotometrically and conductometrically as 3:2. The values of λ_{\max} , stability constant and energy of formation for the complex in acetonic medium were found as 420 m μ , 2.31×10^2 and -34.05 K. Cals/mole respectively. Complex was isolated in the solid form and composition was verified by elemental analysis and by determining molecular weight.

Stereochemistry and electrolytic nature were determined by magnetic and molar conductance measurements, respectively. I. R. spectroscopy was used to establish the structure.

THE structure of *p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal,¹ ligand (L) indicated the chelating possibility at the oxygen and nitrogen atoms of carbonyl and azomethine groups respectively due to the availability of unshared, free electrons. Chelating ability of the reagent has been studied with so many 3d and 4d transition elements²⁻⁵.

Survey of literature reveals that Ti (III) complexes have been extensively studied⁶⁻¹⁰ so far while relatively little work has been done particularly on the Schiff's base complexes¹¹⁻¹⁵ of Ti (IV). It is in this context that attempt has been made to study Ti (IV) chelate of Schiff's base *p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal, in the continuation of our work. Present communication deals with the stoichiometry, stability, nature and stereochemistry of the dark coloured product. I. R. studies have been used to establish the structure.

Experimental

Isolation of Complex: Acetonic solution of ligand containing slight excess over combining weight was mixed with the acetonic solution of metal chloride. Reaction mixture was concentrated under vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride. Dark crystalline product obtained was washed with acetonitrile and purified by recrystallisation from acetoneacetonitrile. Product was dried at few mm Hg. Chelate is insoluble in water, benzene, ether and carbontetrachloride.

Spectral, Conductometric and Magnetic measurements: Spectrophotometric studies were done in acetonic medium with Spectronic 20' spectrophotometer. Conductometric measurements were made with Toshniwal's conductivity bridge. I. R. spectra was recorded in KBr medium using Perkin-Elmer infracord. Gouy balance was used for magnetic measurements.

Preparation of solutions: Solution of ligand was prepared by dissolving accurately weighed quantity, directly. Metal chloride (BDH, Analar) solution was standardised¹⁶ before use.

Elemental analysis: Nitrogen analysis was performed by C D.R.I. Lucknow. Chlorine was estimated as AgCl and Titanium was determined gravimetrically.¹⁶

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Results and Discussion

Composition and Stability: Absorption curves of the ligand and mixture solutions in acetone (prepared by mixing ligand with metal chloride (equimolar) in ratios 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, 2:3, 3:2) showed maxima at $\lambda = 400$ nm and $\lambda = 420$ nm respectively. This bathochromic shift indicated the formation of only one complex in the mixtures with λ_{\max} at 420 nm, which is the most suitable wavelength for further investigations.

The composition of the chelate was investigated by two independent methods: the continuous variations (Job)¹⁷ and spectrophotometric titration (Mole Ratio)¹⁸ methods. These studies were done at 420 nm and 440 nm.

Fig. 1 Job's Method

In the Job's method equimolar ($0.25 \times 10^{-3} M$) solutions of the reagents were used at constant total molarity (10 ml). Absorption curves (Fig. 1) show maxima at Ti-Ligand interaction ratio 3:2. Similar results were obtained from Mole-Ratio method. Absorption plot (Fig. 1) showed break at 3:2 ratio of Ti-Ligand interaction.

Stability (K) of the complex has been calculated by making use of Mole-Ratio results and value was obtained¹⁹, 2.31×10^{24} . Free energy of formation (ΔF) has been calculated according to Van't Hoff isotherm²⁰ at 305°K and its value is -34.05 K Cals/mole.

Verification of spectrophotometric results was made by performing conductometric titration of 25 ml of 0.0036 M metal chloride with 0.01 M ligand in 75% acetic acid. Titration curve showed inflexion at 6.00 ml of ligand added, which evidently indicates the formation of only 3:2 complex. This result, in addition to the verification of spectrophotometric results shows that medium solvent has no effect on the complex stoichiometry.

Results of elemental analysis (Found : Ti, 11.22%, Cl, 33.35%, N, 4.28%, Calc. Ti, 11.29%, Cl, 33.42%, N, 4.40%) further verify the results arrived earlier.

Molecular weight of the complex was determined by the method 'Freezing point depression' in dioxane and value 1288.00 is suggestive that complex molecule is trinuclear (metal-ligand interaction ratio 3:2) and thus final confirmation to the stoichiometry is received.

Stereochemistry and nature : Magnetic moment (μ_e) value 0.67 B.M. of the complex at 295°K is higher than spin-only value (0.00BM) for diamagnetic Ti(IV) spin-paired system and may be attributed to the appearance of new metal-ligand bonds and also due to paramagnetic behaviour²¹ of the ligand which might have arrived by some partial charge transfer with in the molecule. More over this value of μ_e suggests²² $d^2 sp^3$ octahedral stereochemistry to the complex.

Molecular conductance ($\wedge M$) value 72.59 Mhos of 0.0007 M acetic solution, is suggestive for electrolytic nature of the complex. Ethanolic solution of the complex produces white precipitate of silver chloride on treatment with ethanolic silver nitrate solution. Gravimetric estimation of precipitated chloride ion indicates the presence of two ionic chlorine in it's molecule.

I. R. Spectra and structure : I. R. spectra of ligand and complex indicated the lowering in stretching frequencies of $>C=O$ and $-CH-N$ groups from 1653 cm^{-1} and 1613 cm^{-1} to 1600 cm^{-1} and 1504 cm^{-1} respectively during the course of chelation. Therefore evidence for these groups of ligand to be as interaction seats in complex formation is available. Shift of band (doublet) from frequency 820 cm^{-1} . ($1:4$ disubstitution²³) to (singlet) 813 cm^{-1} is the proof of benzenoid changing to quinonoid unit. Conjugation may

be explained²⁴ considering shift in frequency of phenyl skeleton (1573 cm^{-1} , ligand ; 1400 cm^{-1} , Complex).

From the above results only following formula may be the most probable one.

Above structure satisfies maximum coordination number 6 for titanium.

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